

Detecting Fake News on Social Media among Students: The Role of Curiosity, Critical Thinking, and Media Literacy

Katerina Nerantzaki ✉

*Department of Psychology, Faculty of Philosophy,
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece*

Polykarpos Meladianos

*Department of Machine Learning, Faculty of AI,
Mohamed bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, United Arab Emirates*

Abstract

The rapid spread of misinformation on social media poses significant challenges for young users' ability to evaluate information critically. This study examines the relationship between critical thinking, media literacy, and the ability to detect fake news among university students. A sample of 308 students from social sciences faculties completed standardized measures of critical thinking dispositions, curiosity, media literacy, and accuracy in identifying fake news presented in social media formats. Results showed that students with higher levels of media literacy and critical thinking were more accurate at distinguishing real from fabricated news. Better fake news detection was accompanied by greater curiosity and confidence and by lower perceived difficulty when judging online content. Curiosity also predicted stronger knowledge exploration, indicating that epistemic motivation supports deeper verification and learning. These findings highlight the need for educational interventions that integrate media literacy, critical thinking, and epistemic emotion development into higher education curricula to strengthen reflective judgment and information evaluation skills as defences against misinformation in the digital age.

Keywords: *Critical thinking, Curiosity, Media literacy, Fake news, Social media.*

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Introduction

21st century technologies have enabled unprecedented access to a vast range of information on diverse topics, including controversial issues, multifactorial phenomena, and moral dilemmas (Goldman & Casey, 2010). In this context, nearly every global issue has the potential to spark public debate, polarize opinions, and place individuals in decision-making situations that involve complex trade-offs (Muis et al.,

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2021; Pentury et al., 2023). The continuous flow of information, coupled with the ease of disseminating misinformation and fake news, often undermines people's ability to evaluate and process information effectively (Art, 2018). In other words, while the internet and social media provide a broad variety of information sources, the volume and nature of such information can significantly constrain individuals' capacity for critical thinking (Muis et al., 2024). Moreover, users tend to seek and attend to information that confirms their pre-existing beliefs, while avoiding or ignoring evidence that challenges them. This tendency is further reinforced by social media algorithms that tailor the content displayed to match users' previous preferences, thereby creating exposure to limited and often one-sided information (Ku et al., 2019).

In addition, the absence of consistent editorial gatekeeping and the prevalence of algorithmic amplification have facilitated the rapid dissemination of misinformation and fake news (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017; Vosoughi et al., 2018). Fake news, defined as deliberately fabricated information intended to mislead audiences, poses significant risks by distorting public opinion, fueling ideological polarization, and eroding trust in legitimate media and democratic institutions (Lazer et al., 2018). The viral nature of fake news on social media is further exacerbated by cognitive biases, echo chambers, and users' limited critical engagement with online content (Pennycook & Rand, 2019). Consequently, scholars highlight the importance of strengthening media literacy and critical thinking skills as essential tools to combat the spread of misinformation and to equip individuals with the capacity to evaluate the credibility, accuracy, and intent of digital content (Guess et al., 2020).

Media Literacy

Researchers agree that, in the digital age, developing digital literacy skills is essential (Kahne & Bowyer, 2019; Pang et al., 2023; Tommasi et al., 2023). Digital literacy refers to an individual's ability to recognize, understand, and effectively use technological platforms and communication media, as well as to identify potential manipulation techniques (Valtonen et al., 2019). Media can be categorized into four main types: (a) print media (e.g., books, newspapers, magazines), (b) audio media (e.g., music, radio), (c) visual media (e.g., photography, film, television), and (d) interactive media (e.g., the internet, video games, augmented reality) (Pavlik, 2020). Specifically, contemporary definitions of media literacy emphasize two complementary aspects: the capacity to locate, create, and communicate information, and the ability to critically access, analyze, evaluate, and interpret media messages along with their broader social impact (Bawden, 2001; Valtonen et al., 2019). This conceptualization underscores two distinct but interconnected dimensions of media literacy (Sartori et al., 2022). Digital literacy encompasses the skills required to navigate, assess, and produce content within digital environments such as websites, social media, and online news platforms (Wuyckens et al., 2022), while information literacy focuses on the ability to locate, evaluate, and use information effectively (Hobbs, 2010).

Among interactive media, social networking platforms represent the most dynamic form. Their definition is somewhat fluid, as social media tools continuously evolve alongside technological advancements. They can be described as a new mode of social interaction, information exchange, and collaborative content creation serving commercial, political, ideological, social, and educational purposes. Within this framework, promoting digital literacy constitutes a key educational goal. It involves both the ability to analyze, evaluate, and create messages and an awareness of how the information embedded in those messages influences our lives (Sartori et al., 2022). Recent empirical evidence indicates that higher levels of critical digital literacy

significantly contribute to the recognition and/or reduction of misconceptions among young people arising from misinformation presented on social media (Su et al., 2022)

Critical Thinking

The rapid expansion of the internet has substantially heightened the importance of media literacy education (Rasi et al., 2019; Wuyckens et al., 2022). However, the acquisition of media literacy skills is neither innate nor automatic (Guess et al., 2019; Kuhn, 2019). Educational interventions aimed at enhancing individuals' abilities to access, analyze, evaluate, and create media content have generally been found to be effective in improving media literacy competencies (Jeong et al., 2012; Lu et al., 2024). The promotion of critical thinking plays a pivotal role in the cultivation of digital literacy and in the evaluation of the information presented within it (Ku et al., 2019; Tommasi et al., 2023). Critical thinking can be defined as the use of cognitive skills or strategies that increase the likelihood of a desirable long-term outcome; in other words, it is goal-directed and involves higher-order cognitive skills such as analysis, evaluation, and synthesis of information (Halpern, 2013). Critical thinking refers to reflecting on one's own thinking with the aim of improving its quality. For example, in order for an individual to effectively evaluate the quality of an argument presented online, they must first be able to recognize the existence of an argument, assess its logical structure (i.e., the supporting evidence), evaluate the credibility of its source (e.g., the person or organization making the claim), and consider possible counterarguments (Greene & Yu, 2016).

Critical thinking plays a central role in media literacy, as it enables individuals to question the reliability of information sources, assess evidence, identify misinformation and disinformation, make reflective decisions, and form well-informed opinions (Halpern & Dunn, 2021). Evaluating arguments effectively requires recognizing claims, assessing supporting evidence, judging the credibility of sources, and considering alternative viewpoints (Greene & Yu, 2016). Developing an informed opinion in the context of the internet and social media further involves addressing key epistemological questions regarding the nature, boundaries, and sources of knowledge (Ku et al., 2019). The capacity to critically evaluate credibility, accuracy, and bias constitutes a core component of many media literacy interventions (Kahne & Bowyer, 2017). Some programs explicitly teach critical thinking through structured frameworks, conceptual terminology, and targeted reasoning exercises (Tully et al., 2020), while others embed these skills more implicitly through activities such as assessing the reliability of news sources, identifying persuasive or manipulative strategies, and engaging in reflective discussions about media content (McGrew et al., 2018).

Curiosity

Curiosity, as a central epistemic emotion, reflects the intrinsic desire to acquire new knowledge and resolve uncertainty (Litman, 2008; Loewenstein, 1994). It arises when individuals experience a gap between what they currently know and what they want to know; a state that generates a motivational drive to seek information and close that gap (Berlyne, 1960; Grossnickle, 2016). In cognitive terms, curiosity functions as a self-regulatory mechanism that sustains attention, promotes persistence, and enhances learning through active exploration (Vogl et al., 2020; Pekrun et al., 2017). Within digital and educational contexts, curiosity fosters engagement with complex or ambiguous information, encouraging learners to analyze, question, and verify new knowledge rather than accept it at face value (Jirout & Klahr, 2012; Kang et al., 2009). By stimulating deeper cognitive processing, curiosity transforms uncertainty into an

opportunity for intellectual growth and epistemic development, thus contributing to flexible and adaptive thinking in the face of informational challenges (Nerantzaki et al., 2024, 2025).

Media Literacy, Critical Thinking, and Curiosity in Fake News Detection

The proliferation of fake news on social media has become one of the most pressing challenges of the digital age. Fake news is deliberately false or misleading information designed to deceive audiences can distort public opinion, amplify polarization, and erode trust in legitimate journalism and democratic institutions (Lazer et al., 2018; Pennycook & Rand, 2021). Its viral spread is facilitated by social media algorithms that promote emotionally charged or sensational content, often without fact-checking mechanisms (Nerantzaki & Meladianos, 2025; Vosoughi et al., 2018). The speed and volume of online information make it difficult for individuals, particularly younger users, to distinguish credible news from misinformation. Consequently, investigating the cognitive and emotional factors that enable individuals to detect fake news is of critical importance. Recent research emphasizes that the ability to discern misinformation depends not only on factual knowledge but also on higher-order reasoning skills, epistemic awareness, and motivational factors such as curiosity (Bago et al., 2020; Guess et al., 2020).

Media literacy has emerged as one of the strongest educational defenses against misinformation. It encompasses the ability to access, analyze, evaluate, and create media messages, as well as to understand how media systems influence information flow and public perception (Hobbs, 2010; Kahne & Bowyer, 2019). Individuals with higher levels of media literacy are better equipped to recognize bias, identify persuasive or manipulative techniques, and cross-check multiple sources before forming judgments (Jeong et al., 2012; Wuyckens et al., 2022). Empirical studies show that media literacy interventions can significantly improve users' capacity to evaluate the credibility of online information and reduce susceptibility to fake news (Jones-Jang et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2024). Furthermore, media literacy interacts with epistemic beliefs, the understanding of how knowledge is constructed and validated, by fostering awareness that information can be uncertain, contextual, and subject to revision. This epistemic awareness enables individuals to approach news content more reflectively rather than accepting or rejecting it impulsively.

Critical thinking further complements media literacy by providing the cognitive tools necessary for systematic information evaluation. It involves the ability to analyze arguments, assess evidence, and make reasoned judgments based on logic rather than emotion or authority (Halpern & Dunn, 2021). In the context of social media, where misinformation often appeals to intuition or emotional resonance, critical thinking enables users to question the plausibility of claims and scrutinize their sources (Greene & Yu, 2016; Pennycook & Rand, 2019). Studies indicate that individuals with stronger critical thinking dispositions are less likely to believe and share fake news, even when it aligns with their preexisting views (Bronstein et al., 2019).

Finally, curiosity, as an epistemic emotion, plays a motivational role in the detection of misinformation. When individuals encounter ambiguous or contradictory information, curiosity can prompt them to seek clarification, verify facts, and explore alternative perspectives (Litman, 2008; Vogl et al., 2020). This emotional drive encourages deeper engagement with information rather than passive consumption, serving as a catalyst for reflective judgment and evidence-based reasoning (Muis et al., 2018; Stergiadou et al., 2023). However, curiosity must be supported by cognitive skills and epistemic

awareness, without these, information seeking may remain superficial or reinforce exposure to unreliable sources. Together, media literacy, critical thinking, and curiosity form a synergistic framework for understanding how individuals navigate complex online environments and resist the influence of misinformation.

The Present Study

The present study investigates the relationships among critical thinking, media literacy, and curiosity, in predicting university students' ability to detect fake news on social media. Although social platforms have become dominant sources of information for young adults, limited research has examined how students' cognitive dispositions, emotional engagement, and evaluative skills influence their ability to discern misinformation. Building on prior work in critical thinking and media literacy, this study explores how these factors shape students' accuracy in identifying fake news, their emotional responses, and their confidence in assessing online content reliability.

Aims and Hypotheses

Grounded in the theoretical framework and previous empirical evidence, the present study aimed to examine the extent to which critical thinking, media literacy, and curiosity predict students' fake news detection. Specifically, the following hypotheses were proposed:

Hypothesis 1. Higher levels of critical thinking and media literacy will positively predict students' accuracy in detecting fake news on social media. Students who demonstrate stronger analytical reasoning and greater awareness of how media messages are constructed and disseminated are expected to more effectively distinguish between credible and misleading news content.

Hypothesis 2. Fake news detection will provoke curiosity and metacognitive feelings. Specifically, fake news detection will provoke curiosity and confidence, and negatively perceived difficulty.

Hypothesis 3. Curiosity will positively predict knowledge exploration, such that students who experience greater curiosity when evaluating news content will demonstrate higher engagement in exploring and verifying information.

Materials and Methods

Participants

The study sample consisted of 308 university students from authors' universities (Mage = 21.80, SD = 3.02). Participants reported using a range of digital and social media platforms as their primary sources of news and information. Participants were asked to indicate their main sources of news. The majority reported obtaining news through social media platforms (44.8%) or Google (38.0%), while smaller groups indicated no regular news consumption (9.1%) or television (8.1%). At a more detailed level, participants reported using a range of specific social media and digital platforms for news and information. The most frequently used platforms were Instagram (37.7%), YouTube (19.2%), and TikTok (17.2%). Smaller proportions relied on Facebook (14.6%), websites (5.5%), Google (3.2%), X (formerly Twitter) (2.3%), and Google News (0.3%). A priori power analysis was conducted using G*Power 3.1 (Faul et al., 2009) to determine the required sample size for multiple regression analysis with six predictors. Assuming a medium effect size ($f^2 = .15$), $\alpha = .05$, and power = .80, the analysis indicated that a minimum of 250 participants was necessary. Participants were

recruited through convenience sampling from university settings. Participants completed the study online and were recruited via university lessons.

Materials

Critical Thinking Questionnaire (CThQ) (Kobylarek et al., 2022)

The Critical Thinking Questionnaire (CThQ; Kobylarek et al., 2022) is a 15-item self-report instrument designed to measure six dimensions of critical thinking aligned with Bloom's taxonomy: remembering, understanding, applying, analysing, evaluating, and creating. Each item is rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). The factor analysis confirmed the original structure, demonstrating good reliability indices, $\alpha = .87$.

News Media Literacy Scale (Ashley et al., 2013)

News literacy was assessed using Ashley et al.'s (2013) three-dimensional framework, which distinguishes between authors and audiences, messages and meanings, and representation and reality. Six Likert-scale items were adopted, with two items representing each dimension. For instance, the first two items ("The owner of a media company influences the media content" and "Individuals can find news sources that reflect their own political value") captured the dimension of authors and audiences. The following two items reflected messages and meanings, while the final two assessed representation and reality. Responses were given on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The factor analysis confirmed the original structure, demonstrating good reliability indices, $\alpha = .81$.

Emotion and metacognitive feelings

After completing all scenarios, participants were asked to provide overall ratings of task difficulty and confidence in the accuracy of their responses across all scenarios. They also reported their curiosity using a 4-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (not at all) to 5 (very much).

Fake News Detection Task

To assess participants' ability to recognize fake news within a digital news environment, respondents were presented with ten news stories, six fabricated and four authentic, based on Jones-Jang et al. (2021). Participants were asked to classify each headline as either fake or real. Considering that online audiences encounter news through multiple formats such as news websites or social media feeds, the stories were presented in two formats: plain text and Facebook-style image posts. Five stories appeared as text, and the remaining five were shown as image-based posts. To control for potential order and format effects, the presentation format of the ten stories was randomized across participants.

Procedure

The study was conducted with the approval of the Research and Ethics Committee of the authors' university. Participants were first provided with an information sheet outlining the study's purpose, procedures, and ethical considerations. They were then asked to review and electronically sign an informed consent form, during which they generated unique participant codes to safeguard confidentiality and anonymity. Following consent, participants completed a set of four standardized questionnaires presented in a fixed sequence. The estimated completion time for the survey was approximately 15 minutes. Participation was voluntary, and participants were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any point without consequence. Upon

completion, they received a debriefing sheet summarizing the aims of the research and providing contact details for further inquiries. Additionally, prior to the main data collection, a pilot study with 50 participants was conducted to ensure the clarity and reliability of the instruments.

Results

The dataset was carefully screened for missing data, outliers, and inconsistencies prior to the main analyses. In the initial phase, preliminary analyses were performed to examine the descriptive statistics and bivariate correlations among the study variables. Table 1 presents the means and standard deviations for all study's variables. Kurtosis and skewness of all variables were within a normal range, between -2.5 and $+2.5$.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Media Literacy, Critical Thinking, Fake News Detection, Curiosity, Metacognitive feelings, Knowledge Exploration

Variables	Mean	SD
Media Literacy	3.72	1.18
Critical Thinking	3.41	.93
Fake News Detection	6.47	2.30
Curiosity	2.69	.89
Metacognitive Feelings		
Difficulty	2.74	1.07
Confidence	3.18	1.03
Knowledge Exploration	3.60	1.20

Note. All measures were assessed on a 5-point Likert scale.

In the next step, a correlation analysis was conducted to examine the direction of the associations among the study variables. As shown in Table 2, media literacy was positively and significantly correlated with critical thinking ($r = .60, p < .01$), fake news detection ($r = .58, p < .01$), curiosity ($r = .49, p < .01$), feelings of difficulty ($r = .40, p < .01$), and knowledge exploration ($r = .56, p < .01$). Similarly, critical thinking showed significant positive correlations with fake news detection ($r = .61, p < .01$), curiosity ($r = .47, p < .01$), feelings of difficulty ($r = .40, p < .01$), and knowledge exploration ($r = .49, p < .01$). Fake news detection was also positively associated with curiosity ($r = .44, p < .01$) and feelings of difficulty ($r = .26, p < .01$), but negatively correlated with feelings of confidence ($r = -.15, p < .05$). Curiosity correlated positively with knowledge exploration ($r = .60, p < .01$) and feelings of difficulty ($r = .21, p < .01$), but negatively with feelings of confidence ($r = -.16, p < .05$). In contrast, feelings of confidence were negatively related to all cognitive and metacognitive measures, most strongly with feelings of difficulty ($r = -.62, p < .01$). Finally, knowledge exploration demonstrated strong positive correlations with curiosity and media literacy, suggesting that higher engagement in exploratory learning is linked with both inquisitiveness and advanced media comprehension skills.

Table 2. Correlation Analysis between Study Variables

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Media Literacy	-						
Critical Thinking	.602**	-					
Fake News Detection	.579**	.605**	-				
Curiosity	.490**	.466**	.442**	-			
Feel. of Difficulty	.398**	.401**	.260**	.209**	-		
Feel. of Confidence	-.339**	-.194**	-.149*	-.163*	-.622**	-	
Knowledge Exploration	.556**	.491**	.362**	.601**	.271**	-.260**	-

Note. ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$

A hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to examine whether media literacy, critical thinking, and curiosity predicted students' ability to detect fake news on social media, and whether fake news detection, in turn, predicted epistemic emotions (curiosity), metacognitive feelings (difficulty and confidence), and knowledge exploration. As shown in Table 3, both media literacy ($R^2 = .579$, $F = 153.97$, $p < .05$, $\beta = .574$, $t = 6.41$) and critical thinking ($R^2 = .605$, $F = 176.51$, $p < .05$, $\beta = .605$, $t = 3.32$) significantly predicted students' fake news detection performance. Furthermore, fake news detection significantly predicted higher curiosity ($R^2 = .196$, $F = 74.43$, $p < .05$, $\beta = .442$, $t = 8.63^*$), greater confidence ($R^2 = .260$, $F = 22.26$, $p < .05$, $\beta = .260$, $t = 4.72$), and lower perceived difficulty ($R^2 = .149$, $F = 6.99$, $p < .05$, $\beta = -.149$, $t = -2.64$). Finally, curiosity significantly predicted knowledge exploration ($R^2 = .442$, $F = 74.43$, $p < .05$, $\beta = .442$, $t = 8.63$). Overall, these findings suggest that students with higher critical thinking and media literacy skills demonstrate greater accuracy in identifying fake news, which, in turn, enhances their curiosity, confidence, and engagement in knowledge exploration, while reducing perceived difficulty when processing uncertain or misleading information.

Table 3. Hierarchical Regression Analysis with Independent Variables the Media Literacy, Critical Thinking and Fake News, and Dependent Variables Curiosity, Feelings and Knowledge Exploration

Independent variables	Dependent variables	R2	F	β	t
Media literacy	Fake news detection	.579	153.97	.574	6.41
Critical thinking	Fake news detection	.605	176.51	.605	3.32
Fake news detection	Curiosity	.196	74.43	.442	8.63
Fake news detection	Confidence	.260	22.26	.260	4.72
Fake news detection	Difficulty	.149	6.99	-.149	-2.64
Curiosity	Knowledge exploration	.442	74.50	.442	8.63

Note. $p < .05$

Discussion

The findings of the present study contribute to the growing body of research on fake news detection by examining how critical thinking, media literacy, and curiosity interact to influence university students' ability to evaluate information on social media. In line with prior research (Guess et al., 2020; Pennycook & Rand, 2019), the results confirm that fake news remains a significant threat to informed public discourse, particularly within digital environments characterized by algorithmic amplification, cognitive bias, and rapid information sharing. As misinformation becomes increasingly sophisticated, often mimicking the linguistic, visual, and structural features of legitimate journalism, students' capacity to distinguish authentic from fabricated news is critically dependent on both cognitive and metacognitive competencies. This study demonstrates that media literacy and critical thinking jointly serve as foundational cognitive defenses against misinformation, while curiosity functions as a motivational and epistemic catalyst for deeper engagement with information.

Media Literacy and Critical Thinking as Predictors of Fake News Detection

Consistent with Hypothesis 1, both media literacy and critical thinking significantly predicted students' accuracy in identifying fake news. Participants with higher levels of media literacy demonstrated superior performance in distinguishing real from fabricated news stories, supporting previous findings that emphasize the protective role of media literacy in digital environments (Jeong et al., 2012; Jones-Jang et al., 2021; Wuyckens et al., 2022). Media literacy appears to equip individuals with the evaluative tools necessary to recognize persuasive strategies, detect bias, and question the intentions underlying media messages. Importantly, this skill set goes beyond mere familiarity with digital platforms; it encompasses an epistemological awareness of how information is produced, disseminated, and framed to influence perception (Hobbs, 2010; Kahne & Bowyer, 2019).

Critical thinking also emerged as a robust predictor of fake news detection. This finding aligns with extensive literature linking analytical reasoning and reflective judgment to resilience against misinformation (Halpern & Dunn, 2021; Greene & Yu, 2016). Students with higher critical thinking dispositions were more likely to engage in systematic information processing (questioning evidence, evaluating logical consistency, and considering alternative explanations) rather than relying on intuitive or emotionally driven judgments. Such analytical engagement appears essential in digital contexts, where exposure to conflicting or emotionally charged content can trigger rapid, heuristic-based responses. Together, these findings highlight that while media literacy provides the knowledge and awareness needed to navigate digital environments, critical thinking supplies the cognitive mechanism for evaluating content accuracy and coherence.

Epistemic Emotions and Metacognitive Feelings in Fake News Detection

In accordance with Hypothesis 2, fake news detection was positively associated with curiosity and confidence but negatively related to perceived difficulty. Students who performed better in detecting fake news reported higher curiosity and engagement, suggesting that successful evaluation of ambiguous or misleading information may trigger epistemic interest and motivation to explore further. This result resonates with the conceptualization of curiosity as a metacognitive emotion that arises in response to uncertainty or knowledge gaps (Litman, 2008; Vogl et al., 2020). When students encounter incongruent or suspicious information, curiosity motivates them to seek

additional evidence, verify sources, and integrate new knowledge, processes that enhance their analytical engagement with content.

Moreover, the negative relationship between fake news detection and perceived difficulty suggests that students who possess stronger cognitive and literacy skills experience less cognitive strain when assessing misinformation. Their heightened confidence may stem from their familiarity with critical evaluation strategies and their awareness of how misinformation operates in digital media ecosystems. However, excessive confidence could also carry potential drawbacks, such as overestimating one's evaluative abilities and under-checking sources, a phenomenon that future research should explore through longitudinal or experimental designs.

Curiosity and Knowledge Exploration

Hypothesis 3 was also supported: curiosity significantly predicted knowledge exploration. Students who experienced greater curiosity in response to news content engaged more actively in verifying, questioning, and seeking additional information. These findings underscore curiosity's role as a cognitive-motivational driver that facilitates epistemic engagement and learning (Jirout & Klahr, 2012; Pekrun et al., 2017). In the context of fake news detection, curiosity operates as a constructive force that transforms uncertainty into an opportunity for reflection and exploration rather than passive acceptance. However, the positive effect of curiosity on knowledge exploration depends on the presence of sufficient media literacy and critical thinking skills to guide information seeking toward reliable sources. Without these cognitive supports, curiosity may lead individuals to explore misinformation-rich environments without the analytical tools needed to discern credibility, potentially reinforcing exposure to false content (Grossnickle, 2016).

Taken together, these findings suggest a synergistic model in which media literacy, critical thinking, and curiosity collectively contribute to fake news detection. Media literacy provides the structural awareness of how information systems operate; critical thinking supplies the cognitive reasoning to evaluate claims; and curiosity stimulates the motivational drive to engage with information deeply and reflectively. This triadic interaction reflects a holistic epistemic competence that enables students to navigate the complexities of the digital information landscape. The study thus reinforces the argument that combating misinformation requires not only cognitive skills but also emotional and motivational engagement (Muis et al., 2018).

Educational Implications

From an educational standpoint, these findings highlight the need to integrate media literacy, critical thinking, and epistemic emotion training into higher education curricula. University programs should promote not only the skills to analyze and evaluate media messages but also the dispositions to question, reflect, and seek truth. Instructional approaches such as inquiry-based learning, argument mapping, and digital source evaluation exercises can help foster students' reflective judgment and information discernment (McGrew et al., 2018; Tully et al., 2020). Embedding epistemic curiosity as an explicit learning goal may further encourage students to approach uncertainty as an opportunity for exploration rather than confusion.

Conclusion

This study has certain limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the reliance on self-reported data may have influenced responses, as students' perceptions of their critical thinking and media literacy skills may not fully align with their actual abilities in real-world contexts. Second, the sample was restricted to university students, which limits the generalizability of the findings to other populations such as adolescents, working adults, or individuals with different educational backgrounds. Additionally, the cross-sectional design of the study restricts the ability to establish causal relationships between critical thinking, media literacy, and susceptibility to fake news.

Future research should seek to overcome these limitations by incorporating more diverse samples and adopting longitudinal or experimental designs to better understand how critical thinking and media literacy develop over time and contribute to resistance against misinformation. Moreover, employing performance-based assessments or digital simulations could provide a more accurate measure of how students detect and evaluate fake news in real online environments. Finally, future studies could explore the impact of targeted educational interventions aimed at strengthening critical thinking and media literacy, examining their effectiveness in equipping students with the tools necessary to navigate complex information ecosystems and reduce vulnerability to fake news.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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